

DEVELOPMENT OF A STAND FOR STUDYING THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS OF FEEDING AND SHREDDING COTTON STALKS

prof. F.A.Alimova¹, S.R.Nuriddinov², student Sh.Sh.Uzakbaev¹

¹Tashkent State Technical University

²“SEKHRIYO” school

[doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.11234372](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234372)

Abstract The article is devoted to the problem of mechanization of clearing fields of cotton stalks, for which a stand has been developed on which experiments will be carried out to substantiate and determine the main parameters of the working organs of the uprooter- shredder. The results obtained will serve as the basis for the development of a more productive and more compact uprooter- shredder of cotton stalks.

Key words: stand, uprooter-shredder, cotton stalks, parameters, technological process.

A cue feature of the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan is that there are two agricultural crops, the production of which is carried out primarily for state needs - cotton and wheat. In recent years, there has been a slight reduction in land allocated mandatory for cotton production, in favor, first of all, for production of fruits and vegetables. But at the same time, cotton and wheat account 2017 for more than two-thirds of all land allocated for sown areas, orchards and vineyards. Plantings of cotton and wheat in 2017 amounted to 82.2% of all sown areas (excluding gardens and vineyards) of farms. With the acquisition of independence, significant changes were made in the structure of agricultural production of the Republic of Uzbekistan: farms, rental and brigade forms of agricultural management appeared.

Under these conditions, it becomes necessary to mechanize the processes of harvesting to create machines and mechanisms that meet the requirements of a specific form of management, i.e. more economical, less bulky, more productive, energy saving, etc. [3]. An important factor influenced the quality of the technological process is the efficiency of agricultural machines.

When creating new equipment for crop production, it is necessary to refine the designs, because the main requirement for the machines is that the technological process they perform must correspond to the task of increasing soil fertility [2]. Such development is best carried out on special stands, using a variety of design or technological options and striving to ensure that the impact on soil fertility is only positive. In this regard, there is a need to develop improved methods and equipment for testing agricultural machines and their working parts. Such methods should include laboratory and industrial studies.

In the agricultural production of the republic, one of the main roles is given to the procurement of raw cotton, after which the cotton stalks remain. They need to be removed from the fields for autumn-winter events for next year’s harvest.

There are KV-4 and KV-3.6 uprooting-windrowers, designed for uprooting cotton stalks from four rows into a continuous windrow or into sheaves. The KIR-1.5 rotary mower-chopper is used to chop and scatter the chopped stalks onto the field surface. Plowing of cotton stalks as a whole is impractical because during the winter period they do not have time to decompose (rot) and during spring pre-sowing tillage they lead to clogging of the working parts of machines and implements during plowing and are an obstacle to the uninterrupted operation of the plowing aggregate.

The most rational way to clear fields of cotton stalks is the technology of uprooting harvesting with simultaneous shredding into fractions of 0-5 cm, scattering them over the surface of the field or loading them into a transport cart for further use in the hydrolysis industry, for the production of particle boards, for fattening animals, etc. [4]. The issues of harvesting cotton stalks have been dealt with by research organizations and experimental design bureaus; the work of a number of scientists and researchers is devoted to them, but for objective and subjective reasons the problem has not yet been solved. In order to further study the technological process of harvesting cotton stalks and create on this basis a simpler and more compact machine for mechanized harvesting, the Department of Ground Transportation Systems of the Mechanical Engineering faculty has developed a stand on which experiments will be carried out to substantiate the main parameters and operating modes of the working parts of the uprooter- shredder [1].

The main working parts of the stand are the uprooting shovel, the screw corrugated feed rollers, the shredding drum and the transport air-channel. The conveyor serves to feed the stems, which are mounted on cassettes (Figure).

Figure Design diagram of a stand for studying the technological process of feeding and shredding cotton stalks: 1-electric motor; 2-conveyor drum; 3-bar; 4-cotton stalk; 5-knife of shredding drum; 6-guide chamber; 7- shredding drum drive; 8-guide roller, 9-guide shaft; 10- shredding drum.

The technological process of feeding and shredding the stalks occurs as follows: the uprooting shovel frees the stalk from connection with the soil, which in turn is at the same moment captured by the screw winding of the feed rollers. After capturing the stalk, the screw windings tilt it towards the shredding drum in order to begin shredding from the apical part. As it is crushed and fed to the shredding drum, due to the decreasing value of the screw winding pitch, the stalk is straightened and, having reached the zone of the screw corrugated part of the rollers, is fed to the drum in a vertical position where it is crushed to the end. The crushed mass is transported through an air-channel into a vehicle or scattered onto surfaces. At the stand, the parameters and operating modes of the working bodies will be studied: the diameter and length of the feed rollers, the pitch and number of passes of the auger winding, the length of the feed rollers, the rotating frequency, the relative position along the length and height of the uprooting shovel relative to the feed rollers, the rotation speed of the shredding drum, its width and the diameter, number and shape of knives on the drum, the role and location of the shear plate. The forward speed of the tractor will be imitated by a conveyor with stalks attached to it. The linear speed of the conveyor will correspond to the speed of the tractor when harvesting stalks, which is within the range of 4.5...7.5 km/h. In addition, a methodology for conducting experiments on a stand will be developed to determine the fractional composition of the shredding mass. Based on the results of the experiments, the main parameters and operating modes of the working organs - of the uprooter- shredder will be recommended.

References

1. F.A.Alimova. Traktor va qishloq xo'jalik mashinalari konstruksiyasi. Laboratoriya ishlari va amaliy mashg'ulotlar. O'quv qo'llanma. Toshkent, 2019,-211 b.
2. Ксенович М.П. и др. Машиностроение - Энциклопедия. Том 4-16. Сельскохозяйственные машины и оборудования. М.: Машиностроение. 2002. 720 с.
3. Постановление президента Республики Узбекистан 11.05.2018 «О мерах по дальнейшему совершенствованию механизмов своевременного оснащения сельского хозяйства сельскохозяйственной техникой»
4. М.Нурмухаммедов. «Экономическая эффективность комплексной промышленной переработки отходов хлопчатника». Диссертация, Ташкент, 2007,-190 с.